

The Popularisation of Space - A European Perspective¹

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Abstract

It is a legitimate question to ask, whether space is really popular in Europe. But why should it be? This viewpoint tackles both the whether and the why. It looks at deficiencies as well as advancements in communicating space to the European public and decision-makers. Before anything else, it provides an idea of the aim to make space (even more) popular in Europe, reflecting the continent's development and identity

Keywords:

Space Popularisation, European Identity, space activities, astronauts, space education, younger generation

1. What is popular today?

You like astronauts? Of course, you do. And certainly, you can even be characterized as being part of the Apollo generation, which does not necessarily require a birthdate before 1960, but which rather means that the Moon landing is a paramount personal memory, whether it was actually witnessed or not. In this respect, the entire space community, whether 70 or 20 years old, is part of the Apollo generation. So, if you ask this space community, what makes space popular, one there is unanimous consent: astronauts!

But is that still valid for the broader public of today and even more so for the young? Astronauts, most fortunately, still draw crowds wherever they speak and share their experience. For many, they are role models. Not the heroes of the 1960s and of today's Hollywood movies, but men and women who have made a special experience. This astronaut generation is not regarded as one of outward explorers, leaving the Earth and leaving Earth orbit. They are regarded as explorers with the direction Earth. They can share and are requested to share with us their view on Earth for understanding its vulnerability and the arbitrariness of frontiers and nationalism. People want them to provide them with a global identity and inspiration.

But is human spaceflight all there is or all that should be popular about space activities, which have developed and extended so tremendously during the past decades? Can anything else than astronauts compete with what is popular today? And what is actually popular today? Are Soccer players or rock stars more popular than space? Are games more popular than the real stuff?

Ask any young person, how much they like the websites of the space agencies. If they actually have ever visited them, they might regard them as being from the Stone Age. If

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not, landing on Mars or a comet, any sports star has more followers than all space agencies put together. But is this a measure for popularity? Competing for attention in a smart and modern way and popularity could therefore be the motto for the space community.

2. Why should space be popular?

When dropping the word lobbying, the intention should be clear. It shall not refer to the pejorative use of the term meaning to viciously get money, benefits or undeserved privileges with which it is usually associated in Europe. It shall be the understanding that the space community wants to popularise space, because it is fully convinced of the positive effects space utilization has on society and the benefits which are derived from space for economics, sustainability, progress and prosperity. From this perspective, it is legitimate to make efforts (and spend money, the tax payers' money) to popularise space, because it has more the character of information, dissemination and education.

When looking at education, the approach and the intentions are even more diverse in Europe. Space as an attractive tool for education shall certainly lead to develop the future workforce in the space sector. Concepts for space as a tool for education are however mostly seen altruistically by the space agencies in their education programmes in that a clear objective is to raise the interest of young people in all the STEM (science, technology, engineering and mathematics) fields, even if the high school student attracted by space in his or her curriculum will not automatically become a rocket scientist, but may turn out to be a biologist or a civil engineer.

And here we are again. As the astronauts are ambassadors of an idea and an ideal, education with and through space is also dedicated to a broader benefit. These are good preconditions, one may think, to run a successful popularisation campaign meeting today's expectation of European citizens.

3. How to popularise space?

The real question is, how to do it? It does not help anymore if governments advertise for it. Also putting publicity in newspapers and on TV is not really promising. To give the last point a different spin: space can become the background for advertisement, but for this, it has to be popular already. Space has seen limousines on the Moon or beer-drinking astronauts watching meteorites hitting the Earth in commercials. Returning to means of popularisation, blogs, tweets and Facebook are not really promising either, since it is done now by more people than there are followers and readers. The current standards of popularisation are not enough for a high-flyer like space.

Popularisation can work through surveys. They meet the double objective of learning what people think and at the same time they engage people. Space in Europe has continuously been a topic for surveys mostly run by Eurobarometer on behalf of the

European Commission. They lead to good information and intelligence. Sometimes, however, the client is happy about the result that almost 100% are in favour of using Earth observation (EO) to monitor the climate, but this delight is immediately reduced, when in the next question zero percent can name a single EO satellite mission.

So, surveys have to become smarter. ESA actually tried that out. In September 2016, it organized what was called a “Citizens' Debate on Space”. On one day in September, around 100 persons met for a day in each of its 22 Member States to discuss space issues under the guidance of a moderator, touching all major aspects of space and thus taking a step further from a normal non-interactive survey. This Citizens' Debate was modelled after an approach applied already for COP21, where the interaction took place in 100 countries. The result was amazing and showed that with a bit of creativity traditional means can be transformed into effective new instruments.

Another instrument are prizes. In Europe, no prize can match the power of the X-Prizes. But Europe learned and adapted for this situation. The Galileo and the Copernicus Masters are the flagships in the field. They promote new ideas in navigation and EO applications. They target entrepreneurship, but they also are an effective tool for disseminating information and messages about the benefits of space applications. Other, much smaller competitions such as the ESA-EISC (European Interparliamentary Space Conference) Award on Space for Sustainability are also a means for popularisation, but they additionally have a side-effect of positive political communication. The highest scores are hit with programming competitions, be it manoeuvring rovers on celestial bodies, be it docking space-craft to space stations. In these cases, European aficionados join with a global community in creative frenzy, which highlight the potential of space as a cool object for up-to-date pursuits.

The most modern means in this respect is certainly the hackathon. While it does not really popularise to the broadest level of society, it can tell stories of space, its infrastructure and its applications. It also provides an excitement, which can be exploited in many ways. This case shows how space in Europe is embracing new means of popularisation, transforming and enhancing them through its special touch and preparing the young generation for looking at space from diverse perspectives.

Apart from the high-end efforts, a well-crafted mix of traditional and new media is necessary to reach the broadest possible spectrum of society as well as the decision-makers. We have to continuously extend our reach through addressing new target groups with new formats and new platforms in the digital as well as the real world. And we have to overcome the negligence of building a trademark for Europe in space, which can only be to make “ESA” the brand around which Europeans' expectations in such a trade-mark converge. It is the a step towards United Space in Europe, where all partners, be they space agencies, research establishments or industry, can benefit from the power of such a rallying trade-mark. With this, co-branding comes naturally to the benefit of all those associated with it.

4. Space, identity and inspiration

One of my last projects as Director of the European Space Policy Institute (ESPI), and one of my favourite ones, was “Space and European Identity”. It was driven by the idea that space can be a powerful tool for building and strengthening the European identity further and better than its little loved institutions and regulations can. A European launcher, a European navigation satellite system, European astronauts on board of a European module at the ISS - all this can help to produce a feeling of pride in joint European efforts, allowing people to feel a bit more European, which is required as a basis for any political integration.

No one should joke about UEFA and the Eurovision Song Contest. They are more powerful drivers for European integration in the minds of the people than any treaty. But only the aerospace sector has such highly-visible joint European technology developments. Popularisation of space can thus lead to direct positive political and societal effects. You want to respond to Brexit? Use space. The United Kingdom has never questioned its membership in ESA.

The second point besides identity is inspiration. Inspiration can take the most diverse forms: scientific, technological, political, ethical or societal, to name only a few. It is what brings societies forward. It is at the basis for an even better future. The Apollo generation from above has received its inspiration from the Moon landing. It worked for many decades. But where is the inspiration stemming from space today? Is it Landsat 7 or Sentinel 1B? Are you inspired by the precision of the clocks operated for GPS and Galileo? You certainly should be. But it is not easy to convince the public.

Maybe the “Moon Village” concept promoted by ESA's Director General, understood as a growing ensemble suited for multiple uses and open to multiple users, can be the next vision for space. It already begun to create a global momentum. Until it deploys its full potential as an inspirational tool, the “overview effect” of astronauts perceiving the fragile and borderless Earth from orbit, re-mains the key emotional and inspirational facet.

You will hardly convince anyone with brochures, websites or a survey anymore. You can do that when you take the time, effort and resources to run something like a Citizens' Debate. Rosetta and Philae inspired. They accomplished a first and they did so unimaginably far away from Earth in breath taking reality. So, inspiration as a means for as well as a result of popularisation is unbeatable. It always is authentic and it makes you wonder what can be accomplished now and what we would like to contribute to accomplishments in the future. We have to make efforts to prepare new narratives that actually touch people, making space tangible and helping to reach the level of human empathy.

5. On the right track?

We want to popularise space. We do that because we are convinced that space is worth being taken account of by as many people as possible, maybe even by the whole society. Not by chance, the Joint Statement between ESA and the European Union of 2016 on a Shared Vision and Goals for the Future of Europe in Space says that “Every single European citizen shall benefit from Europe's space capacities and capabilities.” And the citizens shall know this. But it’s not so much about getting the citizens' consent to spend their money.

It is much more that we, the space community, can and want to provide, almost dedicate, to society to achieve benefits and progress. A noble cause, which we have to justify and reaffirm continuously, through information, innovation, interaction and inspiration. We have to use space for education and making society STEM-friendly. We also have to contribute to the development of identity, a specificity for Europe in turmoil. We have to adapt our methods and instruments and should not be afraid of taking risks and using unorthodox methods. While money is scarcer for communications in the space sector than in other places, we still have the hot topics. The single most important thing to do, however, is to merge the unmatched inspiration of the long Apollo generation with modern expectations and methods. Then popularity comes unfailingly and allows us to make space work effectively for society.

Short Biography:

Professor Dr. Kai-Uwe Schrogl is the Special Adviser for Political Affairs of the European Space Agency (ESA). Before, he was seconded from ESA to the German Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy in Berlin to support the German Presidency of the Council of the European Union. Until 2019, he was the Chief Strategy Officer of ESA in Paris. From 2007 to 2011 he was the Director of the European Space Policy Institute (ESPI) in Vienna. Kai-Uwe Schrogl is the President of the International Institute of Space Law (IISL), the global association of space lawyers from more than 50 countries. He served from 2014 to 2016 as chairman of the Legal Subcommittee of the United Nations Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space (UNCOPUOS) and was from 2020 to 2022 Co-Chair of the Global Future Council on Space of the World Economic Forum (WEF). He recently co-edited “A Research Agenda for Space Policy” at Elgar.